

Coordination Compounds of Uranium(IV) and Dioxouranium(VI) with Nitrogen-containing Heterocyclic Ligands

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Synthesis and characterisation of the complexes of uranium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) with imidazole (Imz) pyrazole (Pyz) and trimethylsilane imidazole (Tmi) have been described. Compounds of different stoichiometries are obtained depending on the uranium salt and the ligand used. The infrared spectral studies ($4000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) established that in all the complexes, the coordination of the ligand to the metal ion is through the pyridine nitrogen in preference to the amine nitrogen. Possible structures of some of the compounds have been discussed in the light of the ir results.

IMIDAZOLE and pyrazole molecules fall in the class of aromatic heterocyclic compounds and the unique structural feature involving pyrrole nitrogen and pyridine nitrogen make them interesting ligands. Though the pyridine nitrogen of these ligands is normally considered to be the coordination site, coordination *via* pyrrole nitrogen has been reported recently¹. The present work describes the preparation and characterisation of the complexes of uranium(IV) and dioxouranium(VI) with imidazole, pyrazole and trimethylsilane imidazole.

Experimental

The uranium salts were prepared and purified by suitable methods². The ligands (Aldrich) were used as such without further purification. The compounds, in general, were prepared³ by dissolving a known weight of the uranium salts in a suitable solvent and adding to it the required amount of the ligand followed by the isolation of the complex as a precipitate. In the case of uranium(IV) chloride, the preparations were carried

out in tetrahydrofuran and handling of the complexes were carried out in a dry-box.

The uranium and chlorine contents in the compounds were determined by gravimetric method as U_3O_8 and AgCl. Carbon, hydrogen or nitrogen contents were determined by micro analysis. The analytical results are given in Table 1. The infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer in nujol using caesium iodide optics.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results (Table 1) show that under similar conditions, uranium(IV) chloride forms 1 : 2 complexes with pyrazole and trimethylsilane imidazole whereas with imidazole a 1 : 3 compound is formed. While uranyl nitrate forms 1 : 2 compounds, with Pyz, uranyl oxalate and sulphate gave 1 : 1 type of complexes. All the complexes are insoluble in most of the common organic solvents. The compounds decompose turning black before melting.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL RESULTS

Sl. no.	Complex	Colour	M.p.* °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
				U%	Cl%	C%	H%	N%
1.	$\text{UCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{Imz}$	Greenish grey	~195	40.8 (40.76)	23.5 (24.28)	17.8 (18.50)	2.2 (2.05)	13.6 (14.39)
2.	$\text{UCl}_4 \cdot 4\text{Pyz}$	Green	~255	46.6 (46.14)	28.8 (27.49)	13.1 (13.96)	1.9 (1.55)	11.1 (10.86)
3.	$\text{UCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Tmi}$	Greenish grey	~170	38.3 (36.16)	21.1 (21.48)	21.6 (21.81)	4.1 (3.69)	8.2 (8.48)
4.	$\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{Imz}$	Yellow	~150	43.7 (44.91)	—	—	—	15.3 (15.85)
5.	$\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{Pyz}$	Yellow	~148	45.3 (44.91)	—	13.9 (13.58)	1.8 (1.51)	16.02 (15.85)
6.	$\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4) \cdot \text{Imz}$	Yellow	~290	56.7 (55.87)	—	13.2 (14.09)	1.2 (0.93)	7.3 (6.57)
7.	$\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4) \cdot \text{Pyz}$	Yellow	~290	56.0 (55.87)	—	13.8 (14.08)	1.8 (0.93)	6.9 (6.57)
8.	$\text{UO}_2(\text{SO}_4) \cdot \text{Pyz}$	Yellow	~300	54.4 (54.84)	—	8.6 (8.29)	1.7 (0.92)	6.0 (6.45)

* Decomposed turning black.

A comparison of the spectra of the complexes with those of the respective ligands (Tables 2 and 3) bring out interesting features. A positive shift in the ν_{N-H} for the bands at 3 280 and 3 066 cm^{-1} in the case of pyrazole, and 3 200 and 3 060 cm^{-1} for imidazole clearly indicate the non-involvement of the pyrrole nitrogen in bonding to the uranium atom. The ring stretching vibrations due to $\nu_{\sigma=\sigma}$ and $\nu_{\sigma=N}$ in the region 1 540-1 324 cm^{-1} for the two ligands also show a general trend of moving to higher frequency region for the complexes. The ring vibrations for the trimethylsilane imidazole complex are identical to imidazole complex. This observation confirms that coordination in all the cases involves pyridine nitrogen⁴ and the electrons on pyrrole nitrogen form part of the aromatic sextet and therefore, are not available for coordination⁵. Other ligand bands, such as C-H in-plane and out-of-plane bending, ring breathing and ring deformation modes do not show any significant change as a result of coordination.

TABLE 2—INFRARED DATA FOR IMIDAZOLE AND ITS COMPLEXES (cm^{-1})

Imz	UCl ₄ . 3Imz	UO ₂ (C ₂ O ₄). Imz	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ . Imz	Assign- ments
3 200 s	3 300 sh	3 380 s	3 480 sh	} ν_{N-H}
3 060 s	3 230 s	3 180 s	3 300 s	
			3 160 sb	
1 540 s	1 575 s	1 575 sh	1 585 s	} Ring stretching
1 485 sh	1 515 s	1 510 m	1 510 sh	
1 446 s	1 440 s	1 445 s	1 450 sb	
1 324 s	1 350 sb	1 350 s	1 335 sb	

s≡Strong, sh≡shoulder, b≡broad, m≡medium.

TABLE 3—INFRARED DATA FOR PYRAZOLE AND ITS COMPLEXES (cm^{-1})

Pyz	UCl ₄ . 2Pyz	UO ₂ C ₂ O ₄ . Pyz	UO ₂ SO ₄ . Pyz	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ . 2Pyz	Assign- ments
3 280 s	3 300 sh	3 450 s	3 400 sh	3 425 s	} ν_{N-H}
				3 310 s	
3 066 s	3 230 s	3 390 s	3 140 s	3 100 s	
1 525 m	1 538 s	1 540 sh	—	1 540 s	} Ring stretching
1 485 s	1 510 sh	1 505 w	1 515 w	1 520 s	
1 385 s	1 408 m	1 405 m	1 405 m	1 400 s	
1 345 s	1 350 sh	1 354 sh	1 350 sh	1 350 s	

s≡Strong, sh≡shoulder, m≡medium, w≡weak.

Though pyrazole and imidazole are isomers having pyridine nitrogen as the coordination site, UCl₄ formed 1 : 2 adduct with Pyz and 1 : 3 adduct with Imz (Table 1). Similar adducts have been reported to be ionic in nature³. In such cases, uranium atom can be assumed to have coordination number of six and eight. Due to insoluble nature of these compounds it was not possible to determine their molar conductance. New strong and broad bands in the far-infrared region 255-240 cm^{-1} arise due to the ν_{U-O} and are in good agreement with the literature values⁸.

In the case of UO₂(NO₃)₂.2Pyz and UO₂-(NO₃)₂.2Imz, the separation of 205 and 225 cm^{-1}

in the ν_1 (N—O stretch) and ν_4 (NO₃ asym), respectively (Table 4), are of the same order as reported

TABLE 4—NITRATE INFRARED ABSORPTION BANDS (cm^{-1})

NO ₂ -C ₂ O ₄	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ .2Imz	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ .2Pyz
ν_1 1 485 vs	1 520 s	1 505 s
ν_2 1 030 vs	1 040 vs	1 040 s
ν_3 748 m	755 ms	758 ms
ν_4 1 288 s	1 295 s	1 300 sh
ν_5 723 w	735 m	720 m
ν_6 812 m	815 s	825 s
$\nu_3 + \nu_5$ 1 773 w	1 775 w	1 750 m,b
$\nu_2 + \nu_5$ 1 730 w	1 650 m	1 650 m,b
$\nu_3 + \nu_1$ 2 540 w	2 500 m	2 520 m ^s
$\nu_2 + \nu_4$ 2 296 w	2 350 m	2 360 w

s≡Strong, vs≡very strong, m≡medium, w≡weak, ms≡medium strong, b≡broad, sh≡shoulder.

in our earlier work⁸ for bidentate NO₃ groups having C_{2v} symmetry. In view of the fact that the NO₃ groups in these compounds act as bidentate and the ligands as monodentate, the central uranium atom in these adducts can be assumed to be octa-coordinated with two (o,o) bidentate nitrate groups and two ligand (L) molecules in equatorial plane and the two oxygen of UO₂ in the axial direction

The strong bands in the region 1 650-1 350 cm^{-1} are assigned to carboxylic stretching frequencies in the case of the oxalato-complexes. The bands at 1 490, 1 360, 1 328, 795 and 498 cm^{-1} for UO₂-(C₂O₄).Imz and at 1 505, 1 335, 1 310, 804 and 485 cm^{-1} for UO₂(C₂O₄).Pyz are characteristic for coordinated oxalato group⁶. This suggests that in the complex, the planar symmetrical configuration of the oxalate groups where they act as bridges between two UO₂ ions in polymeric form, is retained⁷.

The presence of coordinated sulphate in the case of UO₂SO₄.Pyz is indicated by the splitting into triplet of ν_8 (1 255, 1 130, 1 010 cm^{-1}) and ν_4 (635, 602, 590 cm^{-1}). Further, the appearance at 1 000 cm^{-1} of ν_1 mode which is infrared forbidden in uncoordinated SO₄ also support the chelating nature of SO₄ in the compound⁸.

In the cases of both the compounds UO₂-(C₂O₄).L and UO₂SO₄.L, the central uranium atom can be assumed to be seven-coordinate with pentagonal bipyramidal arrangement of the donor atoms.

The ν_{as} (UO₂) and ν_{sym} (UO₂) vibrations appear at 940 and 830 cm^{-1} , respectively. In the far-infrared spectra new bands in the region 380-340 cm^{-1} assigned to ν_{U-N} modes are in good agreement to those reported in literature⁹. The bands at ~ 220 and 420-400 cm^{-1} have been assigned to δ_{O-U-O} and ν_{U-O} , respectively.

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